

STRATEGIC MARKETING PLAN FOR DISNEY PLUS COMPANY

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Abstract The Walt Disney Company is one of the most accepted companies around the globe. Known for pushing the limits of creativity and innovation to make incredible entertainment experiences that delight and surprise the population around the world. It is not a secret that Walt Disney Company is the world's most admired and respected company. Therefore, every single thing that bears its name also represents its strong commitment to act ethically, create content and goods responsibly, maintain a respectful workplace, invest in communities, and be good stewards of the world. Last year, in the fall, Walt Disney Company created a new branded streaming service, which was called “Disney plus”. The little more than a week, Disney said the services registered more than 10 million sign-ups. It is first launched in North America, Canada, and the Netherlands. Disney Plus is created to be the exclusive home to stream theatrical blockbusters from Star Wars, 20th Century Fox, Marvel, Pixar, Disney's studio, and National Geographic. Moreover, it is an ad-free and on-demand streaming service.

Critical Company Analyses of Disney Plus

Disney's main goal is to be one of the world's leading providers and producers of entertainment and information, by using its portfolio of brands in differentiating its content, services, and customer goods. It is regarded that, Company's primary financial goals are to increase earnings and cash flow and to allocate capital toward initiatives that will drive long-term shareholder value. Moreover, Walt Disney Company has approximately 1.8 billion shares outstanding and is worth

approximately \$90 billion. With annual revenue of \$41 billion in 2011, the company balances rewarding shareholders through dividends, share buybacks, and investing in current actions.

It is regarded that, one of the most appreciable threats of Disney plus streaming service is that the streaming service market is quite mature. Amazon, Netflix, and Hulu all have long-time experience and remarkable growth over years past. It is obvious that Disney is entering the market late by comparison to the competition; the time that the Walt Disney platform will spend in its introductory phase will be used by competitors for continuing development.

Moving to the next step to analyze the threats of Disney plus is the presence of strong competitors, name; Netflix, Amazon, and Hulu are quite successful in their way and have had the long time it takes to explore what customers want from streaming services. Every single platform's progress of original content comes from more loyal subscribers. Due to the option of automatically-pay, users usually forget that they are paying every month for selected services and simply consider the services a part of their everyday life. Statistics show that Disney plus will face significant challenges after launching almost half of the globe; it should gather loyal consumers for being on the same level as Netflix, Amazon, and Hulu.

“The second aspect of the Company analyses part is its price. Disney plus online streaming service price is more reasonable than other major competitors and it has an entirely family-friendly service, this kind of option may fit a family member’s wants and needs more than current online streaming services do. There are no other services that can offer family-friendly content currently days. Research shows that Disney plus's basic subscription plan starts at \$6.99 monthly compared to \$8.99 for Netflix. At the same time, it assures Disney plus with a unique value proposition that the organization can employ to appeal to families who may be currently spending their dollars on another online platform. It is regarded that, Disney plus has market niche content suggests that may not address each customer. While Walt Disney Company holds enough diversified property that some portion

of the organization could likely address to each individual. The Disney plus service is feature family-friendly content that might be regarded as a dynamic extension of the Disney channel. This indicator may cause some households not to need to subscribe to the online streaming service of Disney plus.”

Critical Competitor Analysis

Walt Disney Company is one the recognized brand recognition and a market leader in animated movie productions, due to its much-reputed success in designing life-like memorable animated characters in films. As above mentioned, Disney launched a new streaming service Disney+. Bellow, Disney plus, and other competitive streaming services will be analyzed.

Streaming wars are in full impact on long-running services like Netflix, Amazon Prime, and Hulu now facing relatively new services like Apple TV+ and Disney plus. Soon other big options will join this list, like, HBO Max, Quibi, and Peacock. It is not a secret that each of them will have its own unique sides and selling points to compete against the streaming giants. It is regarded that, into picking one service over the other is its price, especially in the long term. Disney+ offers its consumers one type of plan that allows up to 4 subsequent streamers on one account, with content ranging from HD and 4K when available. The monthly cost is \$6.99 and \$69.99 for the whole year, which breaks down to \$5.83 a month, And it's the best option of the 2 financially, reviewing its low cost and number of gadgets that can be used and the image quality. While Netflix's streaming service suggests three different options, the first is the basic option \$8.99 per month, which gives streaming on the devices in standard definition, the next one is, the standard plan of \$12.99, allowing 2 subsequent streams, inclusive of high-definition content. The last plan is premium which costs \$15.99 per month that allows followers the opportunity to

stream on up to 4 gadgets at the same time in Ultra HD or HD. Table 2.

STREAMING COMPARED				
	Disney	Apple TV Plus	HBO Max	Netflix
Monthly price:	\$6.99	\$4.99	\$14.99	Starts at \$8.99
Availability	Now	Now	May 2020	Now
Top titles	The Mandalorian, Avengers Endgame, Toy Story, The Simpsons	The Morning Show, See, Dickinson, For All Mankind	Game of Thrones, Friends, Big Bang Theory, Rick and Morty	Stranger Things, The Office, Breaking Bad, 13 Reasons Why
Mobile downloads	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
4K HDR available	Yes	Yes	TBA	Yes (on Premium plan)
Number of streams:	4	6	TBA	1 (2 for Standard, 4 on Premium)

Figure 1 <https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.cnet.com/google-amp/news/disney-plus-vs-netflix-vs-apple-tv-plus-vs-hbo-max-which-streaming-service-is-right-for-you>

Other competitors are, Apple TV+ might have the most limited selection with nine titles, but it's also the cheapest, at \$4.99 per month. But real limitation when it comes to these 4 streaming services is with Apple TV+ which is not available on Android TV, Chrome cast and Android etc. (table 3)

Supported devices

	Disney	Apple TV Plus	HBO Max	Netflix
Android app	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
iOS app	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Roku	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Amazon Fire TV	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Apple TV	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Android TV	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Chromecast	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Xbox One	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
PlayStation 4	Yes	No	Yes	Yes

Figure 2

Moreover, all 4 streaming services sweeten the deal with incentives for clients who are already using specific services. Depending on your profession and unlimited plan, people may even be able to get subscriptions for free. For example, T-Mobile's unlimited consumers get free Netflix, while AT&T bundles HBO on some of its

premium unlimited plans and Verizon is giving a free year of Disney plus. At the same time, another major plus side is that Disney+ (for the time being) is launching with zero ads. According to consumers' comments, they always appreciate ad-free streaming services.

Critical customer analysis

All business or trades are based on one thing - this is customer demand. Customer analysis gives the feedback or points the customer wants. What the customer wants or how the demand is being changed. Walt Disney Company is popular owing to products of its Studios, it is claimed that Disney Company mainly uses, psychographic, geographic, and demographic segmentation to address its target market. Moreover, the Walt Disney Company has a mission- DTCI, which means Direct to consumers & international, the main aim of this segment is to provide customers around the globe with entertainment and sports content they want most, with more choice, personalization and convenience than ever before.

Who are your customers – This step provides you with segmentations including (Age, sex, spending amount, consuming time, and date,) –Creating its streaming is the direct connection between Disney and the customer. When consumers make new accounts information is transferred to the database and collected for segmenting.

Grouping the people according to age, sex, income, generation, marital status occupation if the family. Collected data points to Advertising for all audiences. If the new movie will be for a young aged audience, a trailer should be played on Cartoon channels not in the National Geography channels. The budget should be spent in with high efficiency. According to statistics, Disney plus's majority of consumers are under 30 aged people and households. However, it is the home for all people of all ages to watch TV shows and films across all of Disney's brands, which involve its main Disney brand, its Pixar animated films, and Marvel Studio and Star Wars properties and National Geographic. Moreover, the questionnaire, which polled 1,000 American users in May, noted that interest rate in the new platform was

particularly strong in the 18-to-25-year-old market and households with kids, 2 of Disney plus's key marketing demographics.

Dividing the costumers in geographical basics include State, region, country, market size, and climate. This segmenting structure usually helps to sell the product or service with respecting the traditions and culture of native people. The advertisements which were shown in the United States or Europe countries cannot be shown in Chine or Asian countries. As above mentioned, Disney+ is launched in countable countries like, North America, Canada and Australia, etc. on March 31, it is planned to launch across Western Europe, involving the UK, Germany, Spain and Italy.

Top-Grossing Movies 1995-2019, Adjusted for Ticket Price Inflation

Rank	Movie	Release Date	Genre	MPAA Rating	Total Gross	Inflation-Adjusted Gross
1	Star Wars Ep. VII: The Force Awa...	Dec 18, 2015	Adventure	PG-13	\$936,662,225	\$1,006,872,847
2	Avengers: Endgame	Apr 26, 2019	Action	PG-13	\$858,373,000	\$858,373,000
3	The Avengers	May 4, 2012	Action	PG-13	\$623,357,910	\$713,415,897
4	Black Panther	Feb 16, 2018	Action	PG-13	\$700,059,566	\$700,059,566
5	Avengers: Infinity War	Apr 27, 2018	Action	PG-13	\$678,815,482	\$678,815,482
6	Star Wars Ep. VIII: The Last Jedi	Dec 15, 2017	Adventure	PG-13	\$620,181,382	\$628,253,896
7	Incredibles 2	Jun 15, 2018	Adventure	PG	\$608,581,744	\$608,581,744
8	Pirates of the Caribbean: Dead M...	Jul 7, 2006	Adventure	PG-13	\$423,315,812	\$588,764,432
9	Finding Nemo	May 30, 2003	Adventure	G	\$380,529,370	\$559,944,647
10	Rogue One: A Star Wars Story	Dec 16, 2016	Adventure	PG-13	\$532,177,324	\$556,450,789
11	The Lion King	Jul 19, 2019	Adventure	PG	\$543,638,043	\$543,638,043
12	The Sixth Sense	Aug 6, 1999	Thriller/Suspense	PG-13	\$293,506,292	\$524,581,166
13	Finding Dory	Jun 17, 2016	Adventure	PG	\$486,295,561	\$512,156,365
14	Beauty and the Beast	Mar 17, 2017	Musical	PG	\$504,014,165	\$511,880,606
15	Avengers: Age of Ultron	May 1, 2015	Action	PG-13	\$459,005,868	\$496,031,246
16	Toy Story 3	Jun 18, 2010	Adventure	G	\$415,004,880	\$479,175,469
17	Pirates of the Caribbean: The Cu...	Jul 9, 2003	Adventure	PG-13	\$305,410,819	\$461,408,382
18	Iron Man 3	May 3, 2013	Action	PG-13	\$408,992,272	\$458,292,689
19	Monsters, Inc.	Nov 2, 2001	Adventure	G	\$289,423,425	\$449,635,428
20	Frozen	Nov 22, 2013	Musical	PG	\$400,738,009	\$448,472,628
21	Frozen II	Nov 22, 2019	Adventure	PG	\$438,585,364	\$438,585,364
22	Toy Story 2	Nov 19, 1999	Adventure	G	\$245,852,179	\$437,075,134
23	Toy Story 4	Jun 21, 2019	Adventure	G	\$434,038,008	\$434,038,008
24	Captain America: Civil War	May 6, 2016	Action	PG-13	\$408,084,349	\$429,785,941
25	Captain Marvel	Mar 8, 2019	Action	PG-13	\$426,829,839	\$426,829,839

Figure 3 <https://www.the-numbers.com/market/distributor/Walt-Disney>

In this table, you can see the results of the Demand working Strategy of Disney Company. Year by year the net profit is increasing and it is hitting the pick.

Critical Strategic Collaboration

Customer collaboration is one of the main factors in business; it can be defined as "orienting consumer and seller offer with strategic partnership working together with different companies". After capturing the 5 highest-grossing films of 2018, the company was able to increase net profit to \$ 12.6 billion (compared to \$ 8.98 billion a year earlier). According to the results of the fourth quarter, Disney increased profit by 33%, which is equal to \$ 2.32 billion, and recorded revenue growth by 12%, to \$ 14.31 billion. The total revenue from only three films "Black Panther", "Avengers: Infinity War" and "The Incredibles 2" in the US and Canada earned almost \$ 2 billion. Disney managed to become a market leader, then they will expect even greater success from the new streaming service Disney+.

"Now Disney Plus had big contract with Canal Plus. Disney and French-based giant Canal Plus have strengthened their twenty-year partnership with an exclusive Disney + distribution agreement - streaming service will launch in Western Europe and the UK on March 31."

At the moment, Disney + has started in the United States, Canada, New Zealand and Australia. On the first day after the launch of the service on November 12, the platform gathered 10 million subscribers. The chairman of the council and the head of Groupe Canal + Maxim Saada confirmed the fact of the conclusion of the transaction, leaving a message on Twitter: *Le force est avec nous* ("The Force is with us").

The first news about the deal was the French Publication *Les Echos*, in an interview with the newspaper the head of the Disney + international division, Kevin Mayer, said that this was the second major Disney + distribution contract after an agreement with the American television company Verizon.

"Secondly, Disney Plus's first collaboration with Verizon Company was the most effective contract for both companies. What does Disney Plus' free year sound like? Verizon has announced that they will offer your first year of streaming services

at no additional cost from November 12, 2019, with their Unlimited tariff or when upgrading to Fios Home Internet / 5G Home Internet. Since Disney Plus usually brings you a good \$ 70 for a whole year, getting it as a freebie along with something you might need anyway is an absolute theft. Given the fact that Disney's streaming service is ready.

There are a number of Verizon Unlimited advertisements on offer, but they are all designed so that every member of the family can combine and compare unlimited data plans that suit them best, all without unnecessary pieces. Since tariff plans are what you probably need anyway, getting a Disney Plus year for free with them is a real bargain (just remember that Disney Plus will cost \$ 6.99 per month after this first year). This is especially true when you consider the amount of content you get with Disney Plus: more than 600 films, TV shows, and more, including Marvel and Star Wars movies, will be launched this month. Thanks to the merger of Disney and Fox, you will also receive every season the Simpsons and various National Geographic documentaries.

Contextual Factor Analyses

The Walt Disney Company has chosen a tremendously exciting and quickly affecting period in the political background to make Disney plus platform, when the political and governmental rules do not have a direct affect to successful service when the politics and political structure's atmosphere makes the indirect impulsive effect in business existence in today's rapidly changing world. The most essential sector of the political surroundings to regard is an existing situation of political unrest felt by the populations of the US as a whole for different causes. Make a contributes to a remarkable state of concern among United States population, which also reasons concern in person's social atmosphere, business decision and investments. All of the counted points greatly impact on company's launch of new goods. Moreover, some economic factors may influence the Disney+ streaming service. Nowadays the economy of the United States of America is enjoying decreased unemployed and enlarged customer confidence in the dollar. Last year,

the economy enjoyed rising salaries, job growth and increased customer confidence. These points are excellent for a business hoping to release a new customer output, however, according to the forecast of economical prediction, this evolution will decrease during 2019 and 2020 as the environmental impulsive cause reduces and the interest rate increase. Once the economy decrease and the market turn down, those same families will be made to do much spending on a strict decision, potential customers will obtain the services. This might cause to companies support a bunch of sources to the Disney plus that fits the stage of starting customer obtaining and, ahead the market change, the need to recover from an excessive commitment to a platform that in the long run will not work as well as in the short term

It is always regarded that technological advances play a basic role in current days, it is essential for consumers, for enjoying more technological choices than ever before. As mentioned earlier, there is a fact that children own much technology and access to it. Compared to knowledge ever people have had, because of the period of advertisement breaks on TV is not available, is a thing of the past, children require instant content to hold children attention, which is an important feature to streaming services, and teaches the growing in being popular of child-centered movies on the webs like YouTube(Dickson 2007). Technology has already become the easiest direction to get attention the child, and parents do not question this method but adapt to it quite easily. This situation is undoubtedly a plus circumstance in the technology-developing environment of the Disney plus streaming platform.

International marketing strategies

It is no secret that Disney plus streaming service is using so many marketing strategies, to achieve success and be a strong brand. It is claimed that one of Disney plus's marketing strategies is Globe Marketing Strategy, it is obvious that Disney plus streaming services is already launched in many countries, such as the US, Canada, Netherland, New Zealand, etc. and are planned to launch in multitude countries for coming years. "Global Marketing means the process of adjusting the marketing strategies of the company to adapt to the other countries conditions.

Moreover, International Marketing is more than selling a company's product or service internationally, and it is the fully operational process of positioning, planning, creating, and enhancing your product in an international market. Disney plus streaming service's international marketing strategy approach lets its branches in different markets be semi-autonomous. Secondly, most of the marketing activities, goods and sales are decentralized to enable the organization to meet market needs effectively. The Disney plus company's marketing strategies are enhanced through a bottom-up planning approach, which means, the branches develop their marketing strategies and objectives to enable the organization to gain innovation through local enterprises. The Disney Company positions itself in the global market as a basic entertainment company that suggests high-quality services. And it differentiates its goods and achieves high product quality to overcome competition. Disney+ Company addresses its global marketing initiatives on developing its market share by launching new goods, suggesting competitive costs and conducting sales campaigns.”

It is suggested that an International marketing strategy is the most essential tool for Disney plus the streaming platform for its future success, and there is a multitude of advantages of increasing global marketing strategies.

- By developing an International marketing strategy, the company can enhance the effectiveness of its services or goods. To satisfy consumers' needs around the globe, the company should work hard.
- At the same time, Company might have strong competitive advantages. It is easier for companies to be competing with local markets, but there are countable companies, which can do so on the worldwide arena. As a result, by working globally company will have a strong force in its industry.
- Thirdly, Company can increase customer awareness of its brand, service, and goods, via the net, and users can keep track of the company's progress in the world.

There are numerous tools for Global Marketing strategies, and I will recommend some of them, which are essential for the Disney+ streaming service.

- Advertisement- one of the most essential and powerful marketing tools that can help the company gain its dream of converting its goods to sales by advertising it through various means.
- Price Promotion- it is regarded that; the best method to get a buzz of the goods is by putting up some promotions.
- Make use of tradeshows- there are so many types of products and services that consumers do not buy until they have tested it by themselves, for example, Streaming Services, there are many local and international platforms that are satisfying consumers' needs. That is the situation where tradeshows come into play.
- B2B marketing- is an often used method, used by bigger enterprises. B2B marketers need to know their customers' needs before implementing any advertising and marketing tactics.

Moreover, there are inbound and outbound Marketing strategies.

Relationship strategies

It is regarded that, Relationship marketing is a strategy created to foster consumer loyalty, interaction and long-term engagement. It is created to enhance strong connections with consumers by providing them with information directly suited to their interests and demands and by promoting open communication.

Customer lifetime value (CLV) is most essential consideration for many organizations, as they mention happy consumers are loyal consumers, who not only spread their satisfaction by word of mouth to surroundings, but they also spend rising amounts on the purchase of special products and services over time. Furthermore, as a Disney plus streaming service is launched recently, I think that, it has no loyal customers yet. However, owing to Walt Disney Company so many people subscribed new platform, which is the power of strong branding. For achieving customers' belief and loyalty Disney+ should work on Relationship strategies.

Conclusion

To conclude, Disney Company has worked on different projects until now. However, Disney plus project brought the Company to another level. Now it's time for competitors to create a good idea to compete with Disney. Doing this project about Disney plus pointed me that, marketing and strategy management plays the main role in the company's future authority. Moreover, there are Walt Disney words "Animation offers a medium of storytelling and visual entertainment which can bring pleasure and information to people of all ages everywhere in the world". Finally, Disney plus announced that this is not the end of the projects, they have many projects ahead that are secret to us, which means that this is not the end.

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